

A second look at Braverman et al.'s Theorem.

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Abstract. Let us denote as K_G the upper bound of Grothendieck's constant in the ∞ -dimensional Hilbert space, and as $K_G^{\mathbb{R}}$ Krivine's bound. We examine the details of Braverman, Makhrichev, Makhrichev, and Naor's inspection of the Theorem $K_G < K_G^{\mathbb{R}}$, showing that it holds using the same Pisot-Vijayaraghavan number that determines irrationality of the Riemann zeta function $\zeta(3)$. The authors' inspection assumes König's bilinear form $B_K(f, g) > 4\pi \log(1 + \sqrt{2})$. We prove that the bound and the leading coefficient of the number of primitive Pythagorean triangles and triples in discrete mathematics are isomorphic. Appendix A is the very recent inspection of the same theorem by Heilman. We demonstrate that combinatorics endows the integer that controls the truncation index, conditioning the evaluation of Grothendieck's constant bound, with special properties of triangular numbers, m -Catalan numbers attached to the crystallographic finite Coxeter symmetric group B_2 , Young tableaux, and Gauss-Heegner numbers. Braverman et al.'s and Heilman's proofs use the Lipschitz constant on the disk \mathbb{D} of radius $1/2$ centered at $i + 1/2\mathbb{D}$. We show identities involving the Lipschitz constant, Apéry-type series of reciprocals of type B Catalan numbers, and the golden ratio.

Keywords. Discrete mathematics, Primitive Pythagorean triples, Functional analysis, Graph theory, Grothendieck constant, Apéry constant, m -Catalan number, Young tableaux

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1. Introduction.

In 1953, Grothendieck discovered a connection between Banach spaces, such as \mathcal{L}_∞ , \mathcal{L}_1 , and \mathcal{L}_2 , which yields universal constants, denoted K_G , with applications to other areas such as theoretical computer science, quantum information theory, functional analysis, operator space theory, and harmonic analysis [1]–[31], [53]. Over \mathbb{R}^∞ , it holds that

Theorem 1.0. (Alon, Makarychev, Makarychev, and Naor [3, p. 500 (1)]). *For every $n \times m$ matrix (a_{ij}) and every choice of unit vectors $x_1, \dots, x_n, y_1, \dots, y_m \in S^{n+m-1}$, there exists a choice of signs $\varepsilon_1, \dots, \varepsilon_n, \delta_1, \dots, \delta_m \in \{-1, +1\}$ for which*

$$\sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m a_{ij} \langle x_i, y_j \rangle \leq K_G \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m a_{ij} \varepsilon_i \delta_j \quad (1.0)$$

Let us denote by \mathbb{F} the class number field [37, pp. 1–440] of those universal constants, and by n the dimension of the Hilbert space, $\mathcal{H} \subset \mathbb{F}^n$. Grothendieck’s main result was inequalities [1, p. 47]

$$\mathcal{H} \subset \mathbb{R}^\infty : \pi/2 < K_G < \sinh(\pi/2) \quad (1.1)$$

$$\mathcal{H} \subset \mathbb{C}^\infty : \pi/4 < K_G < 2 \sinh(\pi/2) \quad (1.2)$$

where $\sinh(x) = 2^{-1}(e^x - e^{-x})$, and the lower bound of the complex case follows Pisier’s remark in [15, p. 412]. The exact evaluation of each constant is an important open problem of mathematics. We refer to templates such as [8, A#####] as codes from [8]. Let $K_G^{\mathbb{R}} \leq \pi/[2 \log(1 + \sqrt{2})]$ be the Krivine (upper) bound of Grothendieck’s inequality in the Hilbert space $\mathcal{H} \subset \mathbb{R}^\infty$ [5], [6], [8, A088367]. Very recently, Heilman ([30], **Appendix A**) transferred to the author the inspection of Braverman’s, Makhariчев’s, Makhariчев’s and Naor’s [4, p. 4 Theorem 1.1], cleverly improving those authors’ estimation of the parameter p , making explicit and certified all constants and steps which the proof of [4, p. 4 Theorem 1.1] involved. It demonstrates that the Krivine bound, with a gap $|K_G - K_G^{\mathbb{R}}| \leq 8.23 \times 10^{-457}$, is one of the sharpest universal constants in mathematics. Furthermore, Heilman proposed alternative methods not using the parameter p in [4] and [30], **Appendix A**. According to the adopted method, it yields gaps $K_G^{\mathbb{R}} - K_G < 10^{-389}$ [31, p. 5 Theorem 1.6 (10)], $K_G^{\mathbb{R}} - K_G < 10^{-217}$ [31, p. 5 Theorem 1.6 (11)], and $K_G^{\mathbb{R}} - K_G < 3 \times 10^{-5}$ [31, p. 6 Theorem 1.9]. Based on Haagerup’s ideas, Davie [19, Appendix D] and Reeds [24, p. 2 (2)], proposed the lower bound over $\mathcal{H} \subset \mathbb{R}^\infty$ whose sharpness Heilman [29], and Jones and Malavolta [31] recently studied. Following König, let (Ω, μ) denote a space Ω of measure μ , and as $f, g \in L_\infty(\Omega, \mu; \ell_2)$ a pair of bounded measurable functions over \mathcal{H} . Let $K \in L_1(\Omega \times \Omega, \mu \times \mu)$

$$K(x, y)|_{x, y \in \mathbb{R}^n} := \sin(\langle x, y \rangle) e^{-\frac{\|x\|_2^2 + \|y\|_2^2}{2}} \quad (1.3)$$

denote the odd oscillatory kernel $K : \mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}^n|_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, which is the imaginary part of the Gaussian Fourier transform [2, p. 185], [4, p. 5 (1.4)], [57], [58]. Let us denote by $B_K(f, g)$ a bilinear form $B_K : \mathcal{L}_\infty(\mathbb{R}^n) \times \mathcal{L}_\infty(\mathbb{R}^n) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ given by

$$B_K(f, g) := \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} \int_{\mathbb{R}^n} f(x)g(y) \sin(\langle x, y \rangle) e^{-\frac{\|x\|_2^2 + \|y\|_2^2}{2}} dx dy \tag{1.4}$$

defining $f_0 : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow [-1, 1]_{\mathbb{R}}$ by $f_0(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) = \text{sign}(x)$ then $B_K(f, g) \leq B_K(f_0, f_0), \forall n \in \mathbb{N}, \forall f, g : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow [-1, 1]_{\mathbb{R}}$ [2, p. 185 (1.1)], [4, p. 5 (1.5)], [4, p. 5 Conjecture 1.3]. In 1912, Thue discovered the set of numbers today known as Pisot-Vijayaraghavan numbers [44] which form a closed subset of Parry numbers [45]. Parry numbers have that

Definition 1.1. Algebraic integer numbers [37] denoted β , where

- (i) the orbit of 1 under the transformation $x \mapsto x\beta \pmod 1$ is finite, and
- (ii) the algebraic conjugate $\bar{\beta} < \varphi$.

Pisot-Vijayaraghavan numbers, denoted by either α, β or θ [44], have a small Mahler measure, and tend to satisfy a large number of cyclotomic equations. Their quadratic subset has that

Definition 1.2. Algebraic integer numbers $\alpha \in]1, \infty[_{\mathbb{C} \setminus \mathbb{Q}}$ whose minimal, irreducible, monic, real, univariate, quadratic polynomial is

$$\alpha^2 - p\alpha \pm q \Big|_{p \in [1, \infty)_{\mathbb{N}}; q \in \mathbb{Z} \setminus \{0\}; \alpha \in]1, \infty[_{\mathbb{C} \setminus \mathbb{Q}}; |\bar{\alpha}| \in]0, 1[_{\mathbb{C} \setminus \mathbb{Q}}} \tag{1.5}$$

Example 1.3. In 2011, Braverman et al. [4, p. 11] reanalyzed Krivine’s bound of Grothendieck’s inequality in $\mathcal{H} \in \mathbb{R}^{\infty}$, and confirmed the $n = 1$ dimensional case of [2, p. 187 (2.1)]. Evaluation M_0 of the supremum M of the König’s bilinear form (1.4)

$$M := \sup B_K(f, g) = M_0 = 2^{-1/2} \log \alpha_2 = 2^{-1/2} \log(1 + \sqrt{2}) \tag{1.6}$$

[4, pp. 34–6], [8, A196525], where $1 + \sqrt{2} = \cot(\pi/8)$ [8, A014176] is the Pisot-Vijayaraghavan number called the silver ratio, satisfies the Pisot minimal polynomial $\alpha^2 - 2\alpha - 1$. In 1798, Gauss included in his “Disquisitiones Arithmeticae” a conjecture about the set [8, A003173]

$$\{h_l\}_{l=1}^9 = \{h_1, h_2, h_3, h_4, h_5, h_6, h_7, h_8, h_9\} = \{1, 2, 3, 7, 11, 19, 43, 67, 163\}_{\mathbb{N}} \tag{1.7}$$

Discriminants’ evaluations $-d$ corresponding to the pair (h_1, h_2) let imaginary quadratic fields $\mathbb{Q}[-d]$ imply factors $a + \sqrt{-b} \Big|_{a, b \in \mathbb{Z} \subset \mathbb{Q}}$. Conversely, the subset $\{h_3, h_4, h_5, h_6, h_7, h_8, h_9\}$ implies factors $a + \sqrt{-b} \Big|_{a, b \in \mathbb{Q}}$. Does the set include only nine elements? In 1934, Heilbronn and Linfoot [49] proved that Gauss’ original inclusion of nine elements holds up to $|d| > 10^9$ in the imaginary quadratic field of class number 1. In 1952, Heegner [50] demonstrated that only nine elements exist. Stark [51] proved that there is no tenth complex quadratic field with class number 1. Thus, in 1967, the so-called “Gauss class number problem”, which Heegner had already solved fifteen years before, was solved. Peculiar properties endow the set $\{h_n\}_{n=1}^9$. In 2000, Bertolini and Darmon [48, pp. 109–70] illustrated these in the context of p -adic Dirichlet L -series of modular elliptic curves. Cohen [48, pp. 320–3] noted that Heegner numbers and points are elements of Kolyagin’s “Euler system” linking arithmetic and analytic objects, and Faltings [48, pp. 449–54] explained that Heegner points may provide rational points for modular elliptic curves. The Green function

characterizes a system's response to the presence of a point source. It is ubiquitous in quantum field theory, boundary value problems, and operator theory [55]. In 2000, Kontsevich and Zagier [48, pp. 796–7] indicated the role that (1.7) plays in relation to periods, Hecke eigenforms of even weight, denoted k , and higher-weight Green functions, denoted $G_{k/2}(z_1, z_2)$, with order $k/2$ of the underlying linear differential operator \mathcal{L}_z . We recall that the latter acts on the fixed point z_1 while z_2 is treated as a parameter, such that

$$\mathcal{L}_z G_{k/2}(z_1, z_2) = \delta(z_1, z_2) \quad (1.8)$$

where $\delta(z_1, z_2)$ denotes the Dirac delta hyperfunction or distribution. Applications such as quantum information theory [53] and complex systems theory [54] owe their existence to correlations between spacelike-separated events [11]. In 1985, Tsirel'son [11] demonstrated that, for spacelike separated quantum systems [52] with correlated measurements, $K_G > 1$. Present time quantum information theory estimations of Grothendieck's constants in finite dimensional spaces, rely on regular and irregular polygons and polyhedra used to estimate Grothendieck's constants over real spaces of dimension $d \in [2, \infty_{\mathbb{N}}$ [23]. For the theory of figurate numbers, we refer the Reader to [38]. Many areas of number theory include figurate numbers: binomial theorem and Pascal's triangle, prime numbers, Diophantine equations and Pythagorean triples, Fermat and Mersenne numbers [39], Lucas and Fibonacci numbers, perfect numbers [40], palindromic numbers, magic numbers, theory of partitions [59], etc. Let us denote as $-d$ discriminant evaluations, which let imaginary quadratic fields $\mathbb{Q}[-d]$ be *uniquely* factorable into factors $a + \sqrt{-b} \Big|_{a,b \in \mathbb{Q}}$.

- *Parry numbers*, such as φ and α_2 , in functional analysis and operator space theory, such as Grothendieck's constant formulation in $\mathcal{H} \subset \mathbb{R}^\infty$ [4]–[6], [11]–[14], [19], [20], [22], [28];
- *figurate numbers*, in functional analysis and operator space theory. E.g., Grothendieck's constant formulations in $\mathcal{H} \subset \mathbb{R}^d$, $d \in [2, \infty_{\mathbb{N}}$, such as polyhedra and polytopes in [23], and
- *Gauss-Heegner numbers*, in quantum field theory, for example, higher-weight Green functions $G_{k/2}(z_1, z_2)$ [48, pp. 796–7],

motivate that

Question 1.4. *What number-theoretic properties endow the sign-control step parameter p of the constant γ_p , ultimately determining Grothendieck's constant?*

This article includes a Section 1, Section 2, conclusions, and **Appendix A**. Section 1 reviews known theorems of functional analysis and number theory that we shall use in Section 2. Section 2 shows that, up to a scaling $1/\pi^3$, the leading coefficient of the number of primitive Pythagorean triples and the assumption ground of Braverman et al. main result [4, p. 4 Theorem 1.1] coincide. It demonstrates that number theory endows the number 231 in the sign-control step parameter p of the constant γ_p with special properties of certain figurate numbers [38], inherited by the Grothendieck's upper bound. Finally, we show that the Lipschitz constant L_0 on $i + 2^{-1}\mathbb{D}$ coincides with the ratio $\log \varphi / L_5(1, \chi_3)$, where φ denotes the Pisot-Vijayaraghavan number called the golden ratio. They follow conclusions, open problems, and future research directions. Heilman's [30] recent inspection of [4, p. 4 Theorem 1.1] closes the paper as **Appendix A**.

2. Relationships.

2.1 Primitive Pythagorean triples.

In 2011, Braverman et al. inspected their proof of

Theorem 2.0. (Braverman et al. [4, p. 4 Theorem 1.1]). *There exist $\varepsilon_0 > 0$ such that*

$$K_G^{\mathbb{R}} < 2\pi^{-1} \log(1 + \sqrt{2}) - \varepsilon_0 \quad (2.0)$$

considering the function $H : \mathbb{S} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ given by [4, p. 33 Remark 5.6]

$$H(z) = \frac{1}{2\pi(1-z^2)} \int_{\mathbb{R}^2 \times \mathbb{R}^2} f(\vec{x})g(\vec{y}) e^{\frac{\|\vec{x}\|_2^2 + \|\vec{y}\|_2^2 - 2z\langle \vec{x}, \vec{y} \rangle}{1-z^2}} d\vec{x}d\vec{y} \quad (2.1)$$

where $f, g : \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow [-1, 1]_{\mathbb{R}}$ are measurable functions, and assumed König's bilinear form (1.4)

$$B_K(f, g) > 4\pi \log(1 + \sqrt{2}) \approx 11.075667 \quad (2.2)$$

They demonstrated that, then, one can repeat the proof of [4, p. 4 Theorem 1.1] with H_η replaced by H , to reach the same conclusion. Very recently, as **Appendix A** demonstrates, Heilman [30] inspected and confirmed Braverman et al.'s **Theorem 2.0**. The ∞ -dimensional Hilbert space of Grothendieck's Theorem (for example, **Theorem 1.0**) is an ideal abstraction, whose realizations are spaces of finite discrete dimension or order. For example, the Designolle, Vértesi and Pokutta [23] study. On this ground, we recall a fundamental concept of discrete mathematics [69]

Definition 2.1. (Benito and Varona [70, p. 117]). *A triple $a, b, c \in \mathbb{N}$ of positive integers is called a Pythagorean triple if it satisfies $a^2 + b^2 = c^2$. The corresponding triangle with legs a, b and hypthenuse c is a Pythagorean triangle. A Pythagorean triple (or triangle) is called primitive iff a, b, c are coprime.*

Figure 1 and **2** scatter plot Pythagorean triples. The former, on range $[0, 10000]^2$. The latter, on range $[-1100, 1100]^3$ [72]. In **Figure 1** each dot represents a pair (a, b) which satisfies $a^2 + b^2 = c^2$. In **Figure 2** each dot represents one out of sixteen solutions, obtained relaxing the positivity requirement $a, b, c \in \mathbb{N}$. Based on **Definition 2.1**, it can be demonstrated that

Theorem 2.2. (Benito and Varona [70, p. 119 Theorem 1], [71, p. 19 Teorema 2.2.7]). *The number $\tilde{P}(n)$ of primitive Pythagorean triples $(a, b, c) : a < n, b < n, (a, b, c) \neq (b, a, c)$, is*

$$\tilde{P}(n) = 4\pi^{-2} \log(1 + \sqrt{2})n + \mathcal{O}\sqrt{n} \quad (2.3)$$

A corollary to **Theorem 2.0** follows, showing that the ratio $B_K(f, g)/\pi^3$, coincides with the leading coefficient of the number of primitive Pythagorean triples in **Theorem 2.2** denoted n , and where

Figure 1. Primitive Pythagorean triples, on range $[0, 10000] \times [0, 10000]$. Made with [72].

Figure 2. Detail of all 16 primitive and redundant Pythagorean solutions. (Red) dotted lines border the subset $(a, b, c) \in \mathbb{N}$ in the (red) square of **Figure 1**. Made with [72].

$$\pi^3 = 32 \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(1-4k)^3} = 32 L_4(3, \chi_2),$$

It will be observed that **Theorem 2.0** holds based on the same Pisot-Vijayaraghavan number λ which Apéry [73, p. 13] demonstrated to imply irrationality of the Riemann zeta-function $\zeta(3)$ [8, A002117], [32, pp. 40–51], [33, p. 99], [48, pp. 784–6]. The literature on π^3 includes the article by Hessami Pilerood and Hessami Pilerood [74] involving β -Dirichlet functions, Srivastava’s and Choi’s [75, p. 374 (44)] monograph with an integral representation, and Pain’s [76] article, which connected π^3 to the Pisot-Vijayaraghavan number $\varphi = (1 + \sqrt{5})/2$ called the golden ratio [8, A001622], [45]. Further information in [8, A091925], and [8, A118858].

Corollary 2.3. $B_K(f, g) > 4\pi \log(1 + \sqrt{2})$ is isomorphic to

$$B_K(f, g)/\pi^3 > \log(\lambda)/\pi^2 = 4 \log(1 + \sqrt{2})/\pi^2 \tag{2.4}$$

Proof. Dividing RHS and LHS of König’s bilinear form (1.4), (2.2) by π^3 , yields

$$B_K(f, g)/\pi^3 > 4 \log(1 + \sqrt{2})/\pi^2 = \log(17 + 12\sqrt{2})/\pi^2 \approx 0.35720 \tag{2.5}$$

The logarithm’s argument $\alpha_2^4 := 17 + 12\sqrt{2}$ [8, A156164] is identical to the Pisot-Vijayaraghavan number which [45], in relation to the irrationality of the Riemann zeta function $\zeta(3)$, Apéry denoted λ [73, p. 13]. Hence, we may rewrite (2.5) as

$$B_K(f, g)/\pi^3 > \log(\lambda)/\pi^2 \tag{2.6}$$

(2.6) is equal to (2.4). Based on [4, p. 33 Remark 5.6], one can repeat the proof of [4, p. 4 Theorem 1.1] with H_η replaced by H reaching (2.1). The claim follows. ■

2.2 Grothendieck’s constant bound, Young tableaux, figurate, Gauss-Heegner and m -Catalan numbers.

Section 2.2 shows that special cases of

- *triangular, hexagonal, and octahedral figurate numbers*, respectively T_{21}, H_{11} , and O_7 [38];
- *standard Young tableaux* of shape $(21, 1, 1)$, denoted $f^{(21,1,1)}$ [59], [60];
- *ordered products and sums of subsets of Gauss-Heegner numbers* [48, pp. 109–70 320–3 449–54 796–7]–[51];

enter in the sign-control step parameter p of the constant γ_p , ultimately evaluating the upper bound of Grothendieck’s inequality in Braverman et al. [4], and in Heilman’s **Appendix A**, [30].

Lemma 2.4. *Let us denote as $\{T_i, H_j, O_k\}$ a triple of figurate numbers, respectively triangular, hexagonal and octahedral, in general defined as*

$$\{T_i, H_j, O_k\} = \left\{ \binom{i+1}{2}, j(2j-1), \frac{k}{3}(2k^2+1) \right\} \Big|_{i,j,k \in [1, \infty)_{\mathbb{N}}} \tag{2.7}$$

Let f^λ denote the number of standard Young tableaux of shape $\lambda = (2n-1, 1, 1) |_{n \in [1, \infty)_{\mathbb{N}}}$, and as

$$\{h_l\}_{l=1}^9 = \{1, 2, 3, 7, 11, 19, 43, 67, 163\} \tag{2.8}$$

the finite sequence of Gauss-Heegner numbers. Then, those identities hold

$$T_{21} = H_{11} = O_7 = \frac{\rho^{\prod_{l=3}^5 h_l}}{h_2} \left[\left(\prod_{l=3}^5 h_l \right)! \right]^{-1} = h_3 h_4 h_5 = \sum_{l=8}^1 h_l = h_8 + h_9 + h_1 \tag{2.9}$$

Proof. The twenty-first triangular number T_{21} [8, A000217], [38, pp. 1–2 6 78 89] reads

$$T_{21} := \binom{n+1}{2} \Big|_{n=21} = \sum_{k=1}^n k = \frac{n}{2}(n+1) = \binom{22}{2} = 231 \tag{2.10}$$

Figure 3. Realization of the 21st triangular number $T_{21} = 231$ in a region of the plane \mathbb{R}^2 . An equilateral triangle, 21 dots on each external edge.

The realization of T_{21} in \mathbb{R}^2 is the equilateral triangle in **Figure 3**. Different properties endow T_{21} in

- *functional analysis*, as the number of symmetric bilinear forms on a 21-dimensional vector space \mathbb{R}^{21} , and as the dimension of the vector space of symmetric 21×21 matrices;
- *algebraic geometry*, as genus number of the Fermat curve $x^{23} + y^{23} = 1$ in the complex projective space $\mathbb{C}P^{21}$;
- *analytic combinatorics*, as binomial coefficient, $\binom{n+1}{2} \Big|_{n=21}$.

The eleventh hexagonal number H_{11} [8, A000384], [38, pp. 2 6 92] reads

$$H_{11} = n(2n - 1) = 11(22 - 1) = 231 \tag{2.11}$$

In the space \mathbb{R}^2 the realization of H_{11} is a regular hexagon. The eleventh hexagonal number is an even perfect number [40], equivalent to an elementary function of a Mersenne prime [39]. The seventh octahedral number, denoted O_7 [8, A005900], [38, pp. 105 140 201] is

$$O_7 = 3^{-1}n(2n^2 + 1)|_{n=7} = 3^{-1} \times 7(2 \times 49 + 1) = 231 \tag{2.12}$$

which, in the space \mathbb{R}^3 , has geometrical realization as a regular octahedron. Let us denote as $C_{B_2}^{(m)}$ those symmetric functions in q and t , with positive integer coefficients, which give a Fuss-Catalan q,t -extension of classical Catalan numbers C_n [42], [43] that Garsia and Haiman in 1996 called m -Catalan numbers [35], [36]. They have that

Definition 2.5 (Stump [35, p. 295]). *A bigraded Hilbert series of a module associated to the symmetric Coxeter finite reflection group $\mathcal{S}_n := B_2$.*

The general formula [36, p. 54 (15)] reads

$$\prod_{i=1}^n \frac{e_i + mh + 1}{e_i + 1} \tag{2.13}$$

Davis discusses the symmetric Coxeter finite group B_2 generated by reflections in [47, pp. 319–22 411–3], with relevant examples in [47, p. 87 Example 6.7.2], [47, p. 124 Example 7.4.3], [47, p. 124 Example 7.4.5]. Hexagonal, triangular, octahedral numbers, and the number $f^{(21,1,1)}$ of standard Young tableaux of shape $\lambda = (21, 1, 1)$ therefore have the same cardinality 231

$$T_{21} = H_{11} = O_7 = f^{(21,1,1)} = 3 \times 7 \times 11 = 231 \tag{2.14}$$

(2.14) is equal to (2.8). Three primes factor out 231. Fundamental sequences, such as Mersenne [8, A000043] and Fermat [8, A019434] miss, respectively, one and two out of three factors. Comparison of (2.16) and (1.7) shows that the former includes an *ordered* subset of Gauss-Heegner’s numbers [8, A003173], [48, pp. 109–70 320–3 449–54 796–7]–[51]

$$\prod_{l=3}^5 h_l = h_3 h_4 h_5 = 3 \times 7 \times 11 = 231 \tag{2.15}$$

and a distinct ordered subset whose cyclical sum

$$\sum_{l=8}^1 h_l = h_8 + h_9 + h_1 = 67 + 163 + 1 = 231 \tag{2.16}$$

Hence, we may write (2.15) and (2.16) as

$$\prod_{l=3}^5 h_l = \sum_{l=8}^1 h_l = 231 \tag{2.17}$$

(2.17) is equal to (2.10). The claim follows. ■

2.3 231 gates to Grothendieck’s constant.

Section 2.3 shows that:

- *standard Young tableaux* of shape $(21, 1, 1)$, denoted $f^{(21,1,1)}$ [59], [60];
- *semistandard Young tableaux* for a partition $\lambda \vdash 3$ with shape λ , and entries $(1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7)$, denoted $s_\lambda(1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7)$ [60], [61];
- *m-Catalan number* or *Fuss-Catalan number*, denoted $C_{B_2}^{(11)}$, attached to the crystallographic finite Coxeter symmetric group B_2 generated by two reflections in Weyl chambers [62], with braid relation of order 4, in the Lie-theoretic setting [8, A000384], [35], [36], [47];
- *triangular, hexagonal, and octahedral figurate numbers*, respectively, T_{21}, H_{11} , and O_7 [38];
- *ordered products and sums of triples of Gauss-Heegner primes* [8, A003173], [48, pp. 109–70 320–3 796–7]–[51],

coincide with the number 231. Thus, defining the extremizer of the truncation index from which the upper bound on Grothendieck’s constant arises. In 2011, Braverman et al. [4, pp. 26–33] explored the decisive role which the constant, denoted p , plays in Grothendieck’s constant evaluation. In 2026, Heilman [30] cleverly improved the estimation of p . Let us denote as M_ϕ the certified bound (A.59) in **Appendix A**, whose Cauchy’s estimate is

$$M_\phi := \sup_{|z|=\rho} |\phi(z)| \leq 155.0302861362 \tag{2.18}$$

$$|c_{2k+1}| \Big|_{k \in [0, \infty)_{\mathbb{Z}}} \leq M_\phi / \rho^{2k+1} \tag{2.19}$$

The right-hand side of (A.61)

$$\sum_{k=n+1}^{\infty} |c_{2k+1}| \gamma^{2k+1} \leq M_\phi \underbrace{\sum_{k=n+1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{0.9}{\rho}\right)^{2k+1}}_{< \epsilon/2} \tag{2.20}$$

is $< \epsilon/2$ for a minimal integer $k = n = 115$ (A.62), **Appendix A**, where the minimum occurs. Sign-control step is required to be

$$p |c_{2k+1}| < \frac{1}{2(2k+1)!} \Big|_{k \in [0, n]_{\mathbb{Z}}} \tag{2.21}$$

which, after (2.19), motivates Heilman’s choice of the extremizer p of the truncation index (A.64) based on the number 231

$$p := \frac{\rho^{231}}{2 \times 231! M_\phi} \tag{2.22}$$

Figure 4. Complete graph K_{22} equivalent to $> 7 \times 10^{26}$ spanning trees. 231 edges join 22

(2.22) suggests the undirected complete graph, denoted K_{22} , identified as 50646 [48], [56]. **Figure 4** plots $231 = \binom{22}{2}$ edges joining 22 vertices. Considering both possible opposite orientations, 462 oriented edges arise. Graph K_{22} is Hamiltonian, regular, cyclic, connected, and equivalent to $> 7.0 \times 10^{26}$ spanning trees. It includes 1540 triangles. The size of the automorphism group of the graph is $|\text{Aut}(G)| > 1.1 \times 10^{21}$. **Figure 5** shows that the adjacency matrix of K_{22} is inverse-diagonal: exclusively diagonal eigenvalues are zero. It holds that

Proposition 2.6. *Let us denote as p the extremizer of the truncation index from which the upper bound on Grothendieck’s constant K_G arise*

$$K_G \leq \frac{\pi}{2\gamma_p} \leq \frac{\pi}{2[\log(1 + \sqrt{2}) + \delta_0]} = \frac{\pi}{2[\log(1 + \sqrt{2}) + f(p)]} \tag{2.23}$$

$$pM_\phi := \frac{1 \rho^{T_{21}}}{2 T_{21}!} = \frac{1 \rho^{H_{11}}}{2 H_{11}!} = \frac{1 \rho^{O_7}}{2 O_7!} \tag{2.28}$$

(v) *ordered products and sums of triples of Gauss-Heegner primes*

$$pM_\phi := \frac{\rho^{h_3 h_4 h_5}}{h_2 (h_3 h_4 h_5)!} = \frac{\rho^{h_8 + h_9 + h_1}}{(h_8 + h_9 + h_1)! h_2} \tag{2.29}$$

Proof. Young tableaux are a central concept of enumerative combinatorics [59]–[61]. Let us denote f^λ the number of *standard Young tableaux* of shape $\lambda = (2n - 1, 1, 1)|_{n \in [1, \infty)_{\mathbb{N}}}$. Hence, for $n = 11$ [60 pp. 412–3 Corollary 7.21.6]

$$\lambda = (2 \times 11 - 1, 1, 1)|_{n=11} = (21, 1, 1) \tag{2.30}$$

Then, the number of standard Young tableaux of shape $\lambda = (21, 1, 1)$ is

$$f^{(21,1,1)} = 231 \tag{2.31}$$

Replacement of (2.31) in (2.22) gives (2.25). In Catalan combinatorics of Coxeter groups the hook-length formula, enables evaluating the number, denoted $s_\lambda(1, q, \dots, q^{n-1})$ [60, pp. 410 Theorem 7.21.2]

$$s_\lambda(1, q, \dots, q^{n-1}) = q^{b(\lambda)} \prod_{u \in \lambda} \frac{[n + c(u)]}{[h(u)]} \Big|_{(1, q, \dots, q^{n-1}) \in \mathbb{N}} \tag{2.32}$$

of *semistandard Young tableaux* [61], for a partition $\lambda \vdash 3$ with shape λ and entries $(1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7)$. Summing over all shapes, (2.32) reads,

$$s_\lambda(1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7) = \binom{9}{3}_{\lambda=(3)} + 112|_{\lambda=(2,1)} + \binom{7}{3}_{\lambda=(1,1,1)} = 84 + 112 + 35 = 231 \tag{2.33}$$

Replacement of (2.33) in (2.22) yields (2.26). In (2.13), setting the evaluations relevant to our case, the m -Catalan number of type B_2 follows [8, A000384], [36, p. 54 (15)]

$$\prod_{i=1}^n \frac{e_i + mh + 1}{e_i + 1} \Big|_{n=11; m=n-1=10; h=4; S_n := S_2; e_1=1; e_2=3} = (2m + 1)(m + 1) = 231 = C_{B_2}^{(10)} \tag{2.34}$$

Replacement of (2.33) in (2.22) gives (2.27) and an extension of the identity **Lemma 2.4**

$$T_{21} = H_{11} = O_7 = f^{(21,1,1)} = s_\lambda(1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7) = C_{B_2}^{(10)} \tag{2.35}$$

Substituting (2.10)–(2.12) into (2.22) yields (2.28). After **Lemma 2.4**, recalling that $h_2 := 2$, replacement of $h_3 h_4 h_5$ and of $h_8 + h_9 + h_1$ in (2.22) yields (2.29). (2.29) shows a seemingly-

“cyclic” character of the indexes l of the products and sums of Gauss-Heegner numbers. Hence, a sequence where the index $l = 9$ has a successor in the index $l = 1$, rather than no successor. Adding such a rule does not change the associations between elements at the LHS and RHS of (1.7). In the multiplicative case of the identity

$$pM_\phi = \frac{\rho^{h_3 h_4 h_5}}{h_2 (h_3 h_4 h_5)!} \tag{2.36}$$

l runs over an ordered quadruple of indices $l(2, 3, 4, 5)$ at the denominator and over an ordered triple of indices $l(3, 4, 5)$ at the numerator. In the additive case the same is observed

$$pM_\phi = \frac{\rho^{h_8+h_9+h_1}}{(h_8 + h_9 + h_1)! h_2} \tag{2.37}$$

The Gauss-Heegner number h_2 factors-out both representations (2.36) and (2.37). Coefficients

$$\sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k}^2 \tag{2.38}$$

of the power series expansion [8, A000984], [39, p. 28]

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{1-4x}} \Big|_{x \in]-1/4, 1/4[_{\mathbb{R}}} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \binom{2n}{n} x^n = 1 + 2x + 6x^2 + 20x^3 + 70x^4 + 252x^5 + \dots \tag{2.39}$$

generated based on the binomial theorem, are upper-bounded as $\binom{2n}{n} < 4^{n-1}$. A subtle point of enumerative combinatorics arises

Remark 2.7. *The infinite sequence of coefficients in (2.39), includes both $(\infty - 1)$ composite numbers and the Gauss-Heegner $h_2 = 2$. If and only if $n = 1$ (2.39) is enabled to generate*

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \binom{2}{1} x = 2x \tag{2.40}$$

We conjecture that this could explain the presence of the Gauss-Heegner number h_2 in (2.36) and (2.37)—a conjecture based on the following lemma. We shall find that the same power series expansion (2.39) has closed-form expressions with the Lipschitz constant L_0 that Braverman et al.’s and Heilman’s proofs use, with the Dirichlet L -series involving the golden ratio $L_5(1, \chi_3) = L_0 \log \varphi$, and involves concept of mathematics as fundamental as that of the differentiation operator.

2.4. Lipschitz constant L_0 on the disk of radius $1/2$ centered at $i + 2^{-1}\mathbb{D}$.

[4, p. 33 Theorem 5.1], is one of the theorems supporting Braverman et al.’s main result [4, p. 4 Theorem 1.1]. It evaluates the Lipschitz constant L_0 of H_0 on the disk of radius 2^{-1} centered at $i + 2^{-1}\mathbb{D}$, and compares that with the Lipschitz constant L_η of H_η . Heilman (see Section A.3.4

Appendix A) inspected Braverman et al.’s proof of [4, p. Theorem 1.1]. Braverman et al. [4] and Heilman evaluated Grothendieck’s constant also, but not only, based on the evaluation of the same Lipschitz constant L_0 (see [8, A010532]) on $i + 2^{-1}\mathbb{D}$ [30].

Definition 2.8. (Evans and Garipey [31, p. 104 Definition 2.4]).

(i) A function $f : \mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}^m$ is called Lipschitz continuous if there exists a constant C such that

$$\forall x, y \in \mathbb{R}^n, |f(x) - f(y)| \leq C|x - y| \tag{2.41}$$

(ii) The smallest constant C such that (2.42) holds $\forall x, y$ is the Lipschitz constant for f , denoted

$$L_n(f) := \sup \left\{ \frac{|f(x) - f(y)|}{|x - y|} \mid x, y \in \mathbb{R}^n, x \neq y \right\} \Big|_{n \in [0, \infty)_{\mathbb{Z}}} \tag{2.42}$$

For $H_0(z) = \arcsin z$ Heilman determines the Lipschitz constant L_0 as (A.50) **Appendix A**

$$L_0 = \sup_{|z-i| \leq 1/2} |H'_0(z)| = \sup_{|z-i| \leq 1/2} \frac{1}{|\sqrt{1-z^2}|} = \frac{2}{\sqrt{5}} \approx 0.894427 \tag{2.43}$$

(2.43) is one tenth of [8, A010532]. Let us denote as c_1 the constant [8, A020789]

$$c_1 := \frac{1}{\sqrt{32}} \approx 0.17677669 \tag{2.44}$$

Let us denote as ϑ the differentiation operator

$$\vartheta := x \frac{d}{dx} \tag{2.45}$$

with widespread applications in the special functions of mathematical physics and in the Sturm-Liouville theory. For example, all classical orthogonal polynomials [65], including the Laplace-Chebyshev-Hermite special case relevant to the evaluation of the lower and of the upper bounds of Grothendieck’s inequality.

In 1985, Lehmer [66, p. 451 (8)] linked the operator ϑ to the power series expansion in type B Catalan numbers [8, A000984], [19, pp. 73–4 Appendix A], [33, pp. 182–9], [34, p. 78], [51], [68, p. 274], [69, pp. 13–88]. He found that two iterations based on the special value $x = 8^{-1}$, generate the infinite series

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^2 \binom{2n}{n} x^2 = \frac{\vartheta^2}{\sqrt{1-4x}} \Big|_{x=1/8} = \frac{2x(2x+1)}{\sqrt{(1-4x)^5}} \Big|_{x=1/8} = \frac{5}{4}\sqrt{2} \approx 1.7677669 \tag{2.46}$$

whose minimal irreducible univariate monic polynomial is $8x^2 - 25$. In 2009, Mathar noted that (2.44) is one-tenth of (2.46) [67]. Its initial thirteen summands’ explicit evaluations are

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^2 \binom{2n}{n} x^2 = \frac{1}{4} + \frac{3}{8} + \frac{45}{128} + \frac{35}{128} + \frac{1575}{8192} + \frac{2079}{16384} + \frac{21021}{262144} + \frac{6435}{131072} + \frac{984555}{33554432} + \frac{10669659}{1073741824} + \frac{6084351}{1073741824} + \frac{219712675}{68719476736} + \dots + \frac{n^2}{8^n} \binom{2n}{n} + \dots \quad (2.47)$$

A type B Catalan number or central binomial coefficient factors out the n^{th} term of the series.

Denominators are a subset of $\{2^n\}_{n=0; 2^0=1}^{\infty}$ [8, A000079]. As of 2026, the eleventh and thirteenth numerators are unknown to [8]. All other numerators, either directly or indirectly, have a relationship to classical or type A Catalan numbers denoted $C_n := c(n)$ [8, A000108], [42], [43]. Until Mathar's [67] correction, several typos plagued [66]. Four out of eleven corrections are relevant to the pair $(\varphi, -\bar{\varphi})$ of Pisot-Vijayaraghavan algebraic conjugates, where $\varphi = (1 + \sqrt{5})/2$ denotes the quadratic irrational [38] known as the golden ratio [8, A0001622], [32, pp. 5–11], [34, pp. 1–2 7–8 77]. Seven out of eleven corrections involve series with central binomial coefficients.

Furthermore, Mathar noted that $c_1 = 1/\sqrt{32}$ is one-tenth of (2.46)

$$10c_1 = \frac{5}{\sqrt{8}} \quad (2.48)$$

which the power series expansion (2.39) [8, A000984], [69, p. 28] generates after two iterations based on the special value $x = 1/8$. Let us denote as $L_5(1, \chi_3)$ the quadratic Dirichlet L -series of the non-principal character modulo 5 [8, A080891], at $s = 1$ [8, A086466]. Its representations include sums of reciprocals of type B Catalan numbers or central binomial coefficient [19, pp. 73–4 Appendix A], [64, p. 10 Theorem 3.5], inverse hyperbolic and logarithmic functions [32, p. 7], [33, p. 98], [34, pp. 1–2 7–8 77]

$$L_5(1, \chi_3) := - \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{n} \binom{2n}{n}^{-1} = \frac{2}{\sqrt{5}} \operatorname{arccsch}(2) = \frac{2}{\sqrt{5}} \log \varphi \quad (2.49)$$

It follows a corollary showing that the Lipschitz constant on $i + 2^{-1}\mathbb{D}$, in Braverman et al.'s proof of [4, p. 33 Theorem 5.1] which supports [4, p. 4 Theorem 1.1], and in Heilman's inspection (see (A.50) **Appendix A**) of [4, p. 4 Theorem 1.1], the logarithm of the Pisot-Vijayaraghavan number golden ratio [8, A001622], the quadratic Dirichlet L -series $L_5(1, \chi_3)$ [8, A080891], and an Apéry-type series with reciprocal of type B Catalan number have closed-form expression. Moreover, up to an algebraic integer [37] factor, L_0 is proved to coincide with the value that the power series expansion (2.39) generates after two iterations based on the special value $x = 8^{-1}$, and with the constant c_1 [8, A020789].

Corollary 2.9.

$$L_5(1, \chi_3) = L_0 \log \varphi = - \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{n} \binom{2n}{n}^{-1} \quad (2.50)$$

$$c_1 L_0 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{40}} \tag{2.51}$$

Proof. Substituting the evaluation of the Lipschitz constant L_0 (2.43) into that of the Dirichlet L -series $L_5(1, \chi_3)$ (2.49), yields

$$L_5(1, \chi_3) = L_0 \log \varphi = - \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n}{n} \binom{2n}{n}^{-1} \tag{2.52}$$

(2.52) is equal to (2.50). $L_0 = 2/\sqrt{5}$ and $c_1 = 1/\sqrt{32}$, hence the identity

$$\sqrt{5}L_0 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{8}c_1} \implies c_1 L_0 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{40}} \tag{2.53}$$

(2.543) is equal to (2.51). The claim follows. ■

3 Conclusions, open problems and future research directions.

3.1 Conclusions.

We have observed that, up to a scaling transformation π^{-3} , the leading coefficient of the number of primitive Pythagorean triples and the assumption ground of Braverman et al.’s main result, coincide, and that the main result is based on the same Pisot-Vijayaraghavan number $\lambda = \alpha_2^4$, which Apéry used to prove the irrationality of the Riemann zeta function $\zeta(3)$. We have presented closed-form expressions connecting the parameter p , in Braverman et al.’s constant γ_p , from which the evaluation of the Grothendieck’s constant arise to the constant 231 which coincides with the edges of the graph K_{22} . For the extremizer of the truncation index we established identities involving standard Young tableaux of shape $(21, 1, 1)$, triangular, hexagonal, octahedral and Gauss-Heegner numbers, semistandard Young tableaux for a partition $\lambda \vdash 3$ with shape λ , and m -Catalan numbers attached to the finite Coxeter symmetric group B_2 . We showed that Braverman et al.’s proof of the main result [4, p. 4 Theorem 1.1] is based on the same Pisot-Vijayaraghavan number that Apéry used to prove $\zeta(3)$ irrationality. Braverman et al. and Heilman use the Lipschitz constant L_0 . We demonstrated that L_0 has closed-form expression with the logarithm of the Pisot-Vijayaraghavan number golden ratio and the Dirichlet L -series $L_5(1, \chi_3)$. Finally, we proved that, up to an algebraic integer [37] factor, L_0 coincides with the value that the power series expansion (2.39) generates after two iterations based on the special value $x = 8^{-1}$.

3.2 Open problems and future research directions.

- Find deeper connections between the complete graph K_{22} (**Figure 4**) and identity (2.22).
- Study the relationships of the adjacency matrix of the complete graph K_{22} and (2.22).
- Investigate the geometric perspective of the m -Catalan number $C_{B_2}^{(10)}$.

- Find deeper reasons (if any) for the Gauss-Heegner number h_2 factoring out both representations (2.36) and (2.37).
- Investigate relationships of the constant c_1 (2.51), in relation to the Lipschitz constant L_0 of H_0 on the disk of radius 2^{-1} centered at $i + 2^{-1}\mathbb{D}$.

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Data Availability. The data supporting the findings of this study are available within the paper.

Declaration. The author certifies that he has no conflicts of interest to declare.

CRedit authorship. Roberto Alfano: Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis.

Appendix A.

An Explicit Constant Chase in the BMMN Proof, by Steven Michael Heilman.

We make the constants in the Braverman et al.’s [4] argument explicit, starting from the previously obtained input bound

$$\sup_{|\eta| \leq 10^{-2}} |\varphi^{(6)}(\eta)| \leq 1.2843271408 \times 10^{17} \quad (\text{A.1})$$

$$\varphi(\eta) = \frac{4\pi H_\eta(i)}{i}. \quad (\text{A.2})$$

With one explicit choice of parameters,

$$\eta = 2.90803934947 \times 10^{-6} \quad (\text{A.3})$$

$$p = 2.82280900060 \times 10^{-436} \quad (\text{A.4})$$

we obtain

$$\gamma_p > \log(1 + \sqrt{2}) + 4.07 \times 10^{-457}. \quad (\text{A.5})$$

Consequently,

$$K_G \leq \frac{\pi}{2[\log(1 + \sqrt{2}) + 4.07 \times 10^{-457}]} < \frac{\pi}{2\log(1 + \sqrt{2})} - 8.23 \times 10^{-457}. \quad (\text{A. 6})$$

Numerically this is

$$K_G \leq 1.78221397819136911177441345297254934079173190977324 \dots \quad (\text{A. 7})$$

which agrees with Krivine's bound to all displayed digits.

A.1. Setup.

Braverman et al. [4] define

$$F_p = (1 - p)H_0 + p \quad (\text{A. 8})$$

$$H_\eta(z) = \arcsin z \quad (\text{A. 9})$$

and for small enough p they show that F_p^{-1} is analytic on $9/10 \mathbb{D}$ and has a Taylor series

$$F_p^{-1}(z) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} a_k(p) z^k \quad (\text{A. 10})$$

They then define $\gamma = \gamma_p \geq 0$ by

$$\sum_{k \geq 1} |a_k(p)| \gamma^k = 1 \quad (\text{A. 11})$$

and prove that $\gamma > \log(1 + \sqrt{2})$. The proof of [4, p. 4 Theorem 1.1] shows that every such γ yields

$$K_G \leq \frac{\pi}{2\gamma}. \quad (\text{A. 12})$$

The only input from outside [4] that we use is the following explicit sixth-derivative estimate for

$$\varphi(\eta) = \frac{4\pi H_\eta(i)}{i}. \quad (\text{A. 13})$$

Input bound

$$\forall |\eta| \leq 10^{-2}, |\varphi^{(6)}(\eta)| \leq B_6 := 1.2843271408 \times 10^{17}. \quad (\text{A. 14})$$

Everything else below is an explicit constant chase through the published argument [4].

A.2. An explicit positive gap in [4, p. 22 Theorem 4.4].

Braverman et al. compute

$$\varphi(0) = 4\pi \log(1 + \sqrt{2}) \quad (\text{A. 15})$$

$$\varphi^{(4)}(0) = 38400\sqrt{2} \quad (\text{A. 16})$$

so, Taylor's theorem gives, for $|\eta| \leq 10^{-2}$,

$$\frac{H_{\eta}(i)}{i} \geq \log(1 + \sqrt{2}) + \frac{400\sqrt{2}}{\pi} \eta^4 - \frac{B_6}{2880\pi} \eta^6. \quad (\text{A. 17})$$

Write

$$A := \frac{400\sqrt{2}}{\pi} = 1.80063263231421 \times 10^2 \quad (\text{A. 18})$$

$$B := \frac{B_6}{2880\pi} = 1.41949314587084 \times 10^{13} \quad (\text{A. 19})$$

Then

$$\Delta(\eta) := A\eta^4 - B\eta^6. \quad (\text{A. 20})$$

The maximizing choice is

$$\eta_* = \sqrt{\frac{2A}{3B}} = 2.90803934947 \times 10^{-6} \quad (\text{A. 21})$$

which indeed satisfies $\eta_* < 10^{-2}$, and therefore

$$\frac{H_{\eta_*}(i)}{i} \geq \log(1 + \sqrt{2}) + \Delta_* \quad (\text{A. 22})$$

$$\Delta_* := \Delta(\eta_*) \geq 4.29244734953 \times 10^{-21}. \quad (\text{A. 23})$$

From now on we fix $\eta = \eta_*$ and write simply $\Delta := \Delta_*$.

A.3. Explicit constants in [4, p. 28 Lemma 5.2] and [4, p. 29 Lemma 5.4].

We follow the proof of [4, p. 26 Theorem 5.1] with the concrete choice

$$r := 0.92. \quad (\text{A. 24})$$

We also write

$$E_n = \{z \in \mathbb{C} : |\Re z| < 1 - 1/n, |\Im z| < n\}, \quad (\text{A. 25})$$

exactly as in [4].

A.3.1. Certifying $\sin(r\mathbb{D}) \subset E_5$ and $\sin(0.96\mathbb{D}) \subset E_6$.

For $s \in (0,2)$ define

$$f_s(b) = \sin\left(\sqrt{s^2 - b^2}\right) \cosh b, \quad 0 \leq b \leq s. \quad (\text{A.26})$$

Since

$$\max_{|z| \leq s} |\Re(\sin z)| = \max_{0 \leq b \leq s} f_s(b), \quad (\text{A.27})$$

a one-dimensional mesh-plus-derivative certification gives

$$\max_{|z| \leq 0.92} |\Re(\sin z)| \leq 0.7988429115 < \frac{4}{5}, \quad (\text{A.28})$$

$$\max_{|z| \leq 0.96} |\Re(\sin z)| \leq 0.8282425938 < \frac{5}{6}. \quad (\text{A.29})$$

Also $|\Im(\sin z)| \leq \sinh|z| < 2$ for $|z| \leq 0.96$. Hence

$$\sin(0.92\mathbb{D}) \subset E_5, \quad (\text{A.30})$$

$$\sin(0.96\mathbb{D}) \subset E_6. \quad (\text{A.31})$$

Since $H_0 = \arcsin$ on the strip S , this implies

$$H_0(E_5) \supset 0.92\mathbb{D}, \quad (\text{A.32})$$

$$H_0(E_6) \supset 0.96\mathbb{D}. \quad (\text{A.33})$$

A.3.2. Explicit p_r from [4, p. 28 Lemma 5.2].

Braverman et al. [4] prove the bound

$$|H_\eta(a + bi)|_{\sqrt{a+bi} \in S} \leq \frac{\pi[(1+a)^2 + b^2][(1-a)^2 + b^2]}{2(1-a^2)\sqrt{(1-a^2)^2 + b^4} + 2(1+a^2)b^2} \quad (\text{A.34})$$

Applying interval arithmetic to (A.34) on the boundary of E_6 gives

$$\sup_{z \in \partial E_6} |H_\eta(z)| \leq 193.6822943625. \quad (\text{A.35})$$

A separate mesh-plus-derivative computation on ∂E_6 yields

$$\inf_{z \in \partial E_6} |\arcsin z| \geq 0.9666807077. \quad (\text{A.36})$$

Therefore, with $r = 0.92$,

$$M_{0.92} \leq 193.6822943625, \quad (\text{A. 37})$$

$$m_{0.92} \geq 0.9666807077 - 0.92 = 0.0466807077, \quad (\text{A. 38})$$

and [4, p. 28 Lemma 5.2] gives

$$p_{0.92} = \frac{m_{0.92}}{2 M_{0.92}} \geq 1.20508454 \times 10^{-4}. \quad (\text{A. 39})$$

For the radius $\frac{1+r}{2} = 0.96$ that enters [4, p. 29 Lemma 5.4], the same computation on ∂E_7 gives

$$\sup_{z \in \partial E_7} |H_\eta(z)| \leq 300.7944582777, \quad (\text{A. 40})$$

$$\inf_{z \in \partial E_7} |\arcsin z| \geq 0.9971640256, \quad (\text{A. 41})$$

and hence

$$p_{0.96} \geq 6.17764466 \times 10^{-5}. \quad (\text{A. 42})$$

A.3.3. Explicit C_r from [4, p. 29 Lemma 5.4].

To bound H'_η on E_6 , we apply Cauchy's estimate with radius $1/12$. The enlarged rectangle is

$$\{z : |\Re z| \leq 11/12, |\Im z| \leq 73/12\}. \quad (\text{A. 43})$$

Applying interval arithmetic to (A.34) on the boundary of this enlarged rectangle gives

$$\sup |H_\eta| \leq 381.8015394237, \quad (\text{A. 44})$$

so Cauchy's estimate yields

$$\sup_{z \in E_6} |H'_\eta(z)| \leq 12 \times 381.8015394237 = 4581.618473084. \quad (\text{A. 45})$$

We therefore take

$$M := 4581.618473084. \quad (\text{A. 46})$$

For R we use the trivial containment $\Omega_{0.96} \subset E_7$, so

$$R \leq \max_{z \in E_7} |z| = \sqrt{\left(\frac{6}{7}\right)^2 + 7^2} = 7.05228288411. \quad (\text{A. 47})$$

Now [4, p. 29 Lemma 5.4] gives

$$C_r = \frac{8M^2R}{(1-r)^2} \left[1 + \frac{16R}{(1-r)^3} \right] \leq 4.07811339 \times 10^{16}. \quad (\text{A.48})$$

As is (A.11), using $\gamma < 0.9$ we may take

$$C'_r = \frac{2C_r}{r} \frac{0.9}{r} \left[1 - \left(\frac{0.9}{r} \right) \right]^{-2} \leq 2.01664948 \times 10^{18}. \quad (\text{A.49})$$

A.3.4. The Lipschitz constant on $i + 2^{-1}\mathbb{D}$.

For $H_0(z) = \arcsin z$ we have

$$L_0 = \sup_{|z-i| \leq 1/2} |H_0'(z)| = \sup_{|z-i| \leq 1/2} \frac{1}{|\sqrt{1-z^2}|} = \frac{2}{\sqrt{5}} \leq 0.894427191. \quad (\text{A.50})$$

For H_η , Cauchy's estimate with radius $1/4$ gives

$$L_\eta \leq 4 \sup_{|z-i|=3/2} |H_\eta(z)|. \quad (\text{A.51})$$

Applying interval arithmetic to (A.34) on the circle $|z-i| = 3/4$ gives

$$\sup_{|z-i|=3/4} |H_\eta(z)| \leq 8.54068663589, \quad (\text{A.52})$$

$$L_\eta \leq 34.1627465436. \quad (\text{A.53})$$

Thus, we can take

$$L := \max\{L_0, L_\eta\} \leq 34.1627465436. \quad (\text{A.54})$$

A.4. Explicit coefficient bounds for $\phi(z) = [z - H_\eta(\sin z)] \cos z$.

We now choose

$$\rho := 1.152. \quad (\text{A.55})$$

A one-dimensional mesh-plus-derivative certification gives

$$\max_{|z| \leq \rho} |\Re(\sin z)| \leq 0.9950381805 < 1 \quad (\text{A.56})$$

so $\sin(\rho\mathbb{D}) \subset S$, and therefore ϕ is analytic on $\rho\mathbb{D}$. On the circle $|z| = \rho$ we have

$$|\phi(z)| \leq [\rho + |H_\eta(\sin z)|] |\cos z|. \quad (\text{A.57})$$

Applying interval arithmetic to the right-hand side, again using (A.34), on 32000 equal

subintervals of $[0, 2\pi]$ yields the certified bound

$$M_\phi := \sup_{|z|=\rho} |\phi(z)| \leq 155.0302861362. \quad (\text{A. 58})$$

Hence Cauchy's estimate gives

$$|c_{2k+1}| \leq M_\phi \rho^{-2k-1} \quad (k \geq 0). \quad (\text{A. 59})$$

A.5. Explicit ϵ , n , and p in the proof of Theorem 5.1.

We choose

$$\epsilon := 0.664 \frac{\Delta}{L} = 8.34296222775 \times 10^{-23}. \quad (\text{A. 60})$$

Since $\gamma < 0.9$ in the contradiction argument, the tail estimate is controlled by

$$\sum_{k=n+1}^{\infty} |c_{2k+1}| \gamma^{2k+1} \leq M_\phi \sum_{k=n+1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{0.9}{\rho}\right)^{2k+1}. \quad (\text{A. 61})$$

With (A.58) and $\rho = 1.152$, the minimal integer n for which the right-hand side is $< \epsilon/2$ is

$$n = 115. \quad (\text{A. 62})$$

For the sign-control step we require

$$p|c_{2k+1}| < 2^{-1}|b_{2k+1}| = [2(2k+1)!]^{-1}, k \in [0, n]_{\mathbb{Z}}. \quad (\text{A. 63})$$

Since $|c_{2k+1}| \leq M_\phi/\rho^{2k+1}$ and the minimum occurs at $k = n = 115$, it is enough to choose

$$p := \frac{\rho^{231}}{2 \times 231! M_\phi} = 2.82280900060 \times 10^{-436}. \quad (\text{A. 64})$$

This is vastly smaller than both (A.39) and (A.42), so all the analyticity requirements in [4, p. Lemmas 5.2] and [4, p. Lemma 5.4] are satisfied.

A.6. An explicit lower bound on γ_p .

Fix the parameters chosen above. We now rerun the contradiction argument from the proof of [4, p. 26 Theorem 5.1] with a quantitative target. Let

$$\delta_0 := p\Delta - L(C_r' p^2 + p\epsilon). \quad (\text{A. 65})$$

With the numerical values already chosen,

$$\delta_0 \geq 4.07123102832 \times 10^{-457}. \quad (\text{A. 66})$$

Note that in particular $\delta_0 < 10^{-100} < 0.9 - \log(1 + \sqrt{2})$. Assume for contradiction that:

$$\gamma_p \leq \log(1 + \sqrt{2}) + \delta_0. \quad (\text{A. 67})$$

Then certainly $\gamma_p < 0.9$, so the same estimates as in (A.10)–(A.14) apply. If we write

$$\beta = F_p^{-1}(i\gamma_p) - i \quad (\text{A. 68})$$

then, exactly as in (A.11)–(A.13), we obtain

$$|\beta| \leq C_r' p^2 + p\epsilon \quad (\text{A. 69})$$

Because F_p is L -Lipschitz on $i + 2^{-1}\mathbb{D}$, we have

$$\gamma_p = \frac{F_p(i + \beta)}{i} \geq \frac{F_p(i)}{i} - L|\beta| \quad (\text{A. 70})$$

Using (A.23) and the definition of Δ this becomes

$$\gamma_p \geq (1 - p)\log(1 + \sqrt{2}) + p[\log(1 + \sqrt{2}) + \Delta] - L(C_r' p^2 + p\epsilon) \quad (\text{A. 71})$$

$$\gamma_p \geq \log(1 + \sqrt{2}) + \delta_0. \quad (\text{A. 72})$$

This contradicts the assumption

$$\gamma_p \leq \log(1 + \sqrt{2}) + \delta_0. \quad (\text{A. 73})$$

Therefore:

Theorem A.1. *For the explicit choice*

$$(\eta, p) = (2.90803934947 \times 10^{-6}, 2.82280900060 \times 10^{-436}) \quad (\text{A. 74})$$

the corresponding Braverman et al. 's [4] constant γ_p satisfies

$$\gamma_p > \log(1 + \sqrt{2}) + 4.07 \times 10^{-457}. \quad (\text{A. 75})$$

A.7. The resulting explicit upper bound on K_G .

By (A.12)

$$K_G \leq \frac{\pi}{2\gamma_p} \leq \frac{\pi}{2[\log(1 + \sqrt{2}) + \delta_0]}. \quad (\text{A. 76})$$

With (A.66), this gives the explicit bounds

$$K_G \leq \frac{\pi}{2[\log(1 + \sqrt{2}) + 4.07 \times 10^{-457}]} \quad (\text{A.77})$$

Equivalently, if

$$K_{\text{Kr}} := \frac{\pi}{2 \log(1 + \sqrt{2})} \quad (\text{A.78})$$

then

$$K_{\text{Kr}} - K_G \geq \frac{\pi \delta_0}{2 \log(1 + \sqrt{2})[\log(1 + \sqrt{2}) + \delta_0]} \geq 8.23 \times 10^{-457}. \quad (\text{A.79})$$

Since

$$K_{\text{Kr}} = 1.78221397819136911177441345297254934079173190977324 \dots \quad (\text{A.80})$$

our explicit upper bound agrees with Krivine's bound to all displayed digits.

A.8. Conclusion.

The Braverman et al.'s [4] proof is fully effective. Using the explicit sixth-derivative input bound above, one can extract a completely explicit parameter choice and a completely explicit strict improvement over Krivine's constant. The resulting improvement is astronomically small because the proof passes through the sign-control step

$$p|c_{2k+1}|_{k \in [0, n]_{\mathbb{Z}}} < 2^{-1}|b_{2k+1}| \quad (\text{A.81})$$

which forces p to be on the order of $1/(2n + 1)!$. The argument is therefore explicit but numerically very weak.

A.9. Summary table.

Certified value	Meaning	Symbol
$1.2843271408 \times 10^{17}$	input bound for $\sup_{ \eta \leq 10^{-2}} \varphi^{(6)}(\eta) $	B_6
$2.90803934947 \times 10^{-6}$	parameter in H_η	η
$\geq 4.29244734953 \times 10^{-21}$	gain in $H_\eta(i)/i$ over $\log(1 + \sqrt{2})$	Δ
0.92	disk radius in [4, pp. 28–9 Lemma 5.2–5.4]	r
≤ 0.7988429115	certifies $\sin(0.92\mathbb{D}) \subset E_5$	$\max_{ z \leq 0.92} \Re \sin z $
≤ 0.8282425938	certifies $\sin(0.96\mathbb{D}) \subset E_6$	$\max_{ z \leq 0.96} \Re \sin z $
≤ 193.6822943625	$\sup_{\partial E_6} H_\eta $ from (A.34)	$M_{0.92}$
≥ 0.0466807077	distance from $\arcsin(\partial E_6)$ to $0.92\mathbb{D}$	$m_{0.92}$
$\geq 1.20508454 \times 10^{-4}$	[4, p. 29 Lemma 5.4] constant for $r = 0.92$	$p_{0.92}$
≤ 300.7944582777	$\sup_{\partial E_7} H_\eta $ from (A.34)	$M_{0.96}$
≥ 0.0371640256	distance from $\arcsin(\partial E_7)$ to $0.96\mathbb{D}$	$m_{0.96}$
$\geq 6.17764466 \times 10^{-5}$	[4, p. 29 Lemma 5.4] constant for $r = 0.96$	$p_{0.96}$
≤ 34.1627465436	Lipschitz constant on $i + 2^{-1}\mathbb{D}$	L
≤ 4581.618473084	uniform bound used in [4, p. 29 Lemma 5.4]	M
≤ 7.05228288411	geometric radius bound for $\Omega_{0.96}$	R
$\leq 4.07811339 \times 10^{16}$	constant in [4, p. 29 Lemma 5.4]	C_r
$\leq 2.01664948 \times 10^{18}$	geometric-series constant from (A.49)	C_r'
1.152	disk of analyticity for ϕ	ρ
≤ 155.0302861362	$\sup_{ z =\rho} \phi(z) $	M_ϕ
$8.34296222775 \times 10^{-23}$	tail parameter in (A.60)	ϵ
115	truncation index in (A.61)–(A.63)	n
$2.82280900060 \times 10^{-436}$	explicit sign-control parameter in (A.64)	p
$\geq 4.07123102832 \times 10^{-457}$	final improvement in γ_p	δ_0
$\geq 8.23 \times 10^{-457}$	final improvement in K_G over Krivine's bound	ϵ_0

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